

Electronic Supplementary Material

Complementary Roles of Mechanotransduction and Inflammation in Vascular Homeostasis

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Supplemental Figure S1

Figure S1. As Figure 2 in the main text, but with an extended schema that illustrates the coupling between Cauchy stress ($\boldsymbol{\sigma}$) and inflammation ($\Delta\varrho_\varphi$) within the present G&R framework.